

LOSS OF NITROGEN IN BACTERIAL NITRIFICATION

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Contrary to the generally accepted idea that no marked loss of nitrogen takes place during bacterial nitrification of nitrogenous compounds, it has been observed that approximately half of the total nitrogen is lost in the nitrification of hippuric acid, oil-cake, uric acid, creatine and fibrin. With ammonium phosphate, sulphate, persulphate and urea the loss of nitrogen is more than half.

This loss has been explained from the view-point that during the process of nitrification, ammonium nitrite is produced as an intermediate product, which decomposes into water and nitrogen. The loss may also partially be due to the decomposition of nitrous acid, especially when the pH is less than 7.

The presence of carbonaceous substances retard the velocity of oxidation of ammonia to nitrate by acting as negative catalysts.

In previous publications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 67, 75 ; 1936, 13, 555 ; 1938, 15, 583) it has been shown that marked losses of nitrogen take place during the nitrification of organic and inorganic manures in soil cultures. Also the experiments at Rothamsted fields reveal that when 100 lbs. of nitrogen per acre are added, approximately 65% are lost without benefit to the soil or the crop.

On the other hand, the position regarding the bacterial nitrification in liquid cultures has been stated by Russell ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth", 1932, p. 328) as follows:—

"The essential facts of nitrification are readily demonstrated by putting a small quantity of soil—0.2 to 0.5 gram into 50 c.c. of a dilute solution of ammonium sulphate containing nutrient inorganic salts and some calcium or magnesium carbonate but no other carbon compound. After three or four weeks at 25° the ammonia is all gone and its place taken up by nitrates. The conversion is almost quantitative, only an insignificant quantity of nitrogen being retained by the organisms."

In order to explain the difference in these observations we have undertaken a systematic research on the problem of nitrogen loss during bacterial nitrification of different substances, both organic and inorganic in liquid cultures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following medium was prepared for the growth of the nitrifying bacteria : Potassium phosphate (K_2HPO_4), 1.0 g ; sodium chloride, 2.0 g., ferrous sulphate, 0.4 g., distilled water, 1000 c.c. and magnesium carbonate, excess (0.5 g. per 100 c.c.).

After shaking the medium, 50 c.c. of it were taken in 200 c.c. conical flasks which were then plugged with cotton wool and were sterilised in an autoclave at a pressure of 15 to 20 lbs. for half an hour. A 10% solution of ammonium sulphate was prepared and sterilised separately. From 1 c.c. to 10 c.c. of this solution was added to various flasks containing the sterilised media by a sterile pipette. For obtaining the nitrifying bacteria, one gram of fresh garden soil was inoculated into each experimental flask. The flasks were then incubated at 35° for a period of seven to eight weeks. A 10% solution of ammonium persulphate or ammonium phosphate was used in a similar manner as in the case of ammonium sulphate. For experiments with substances like hippuric acid, urea, oil-cake, fibrin etc., a known amount of the substance was weighed and placed in the flask containing the medium. The flasks were then sterilised along with these nitrogenous substances. The analysis was performed in the following manner.

The ammoniacal nitrogen was estimated colorimetrically by Nessler's reagent. Nitric nitrogen was reduced by Devarda's alloy to ammoniacal nitrogen and then estimated as above. For total nitrogen, the Kjeldahl method was used. The following results have been obtained.

TABLE I

Ammonium sulphate as the source of nitrogen.

Original N content Soln. Nitrogen.	Ammon. N left.	Nitric N formed.	Total N left.	N lost.	% Loss of nitrogen.
10.0 c.c. 0.2121 g.	0.1328 g.	0.0178 g.	0.1506 g.	0.0615 g.	38.9
7.0 0.1486	0.0776	0.0160	0.0936	0.0549	27.1
5.0 0.1061	0.0289	0.0152	0.0441	0.0620	58.4
2.0 0.0424	0.0031	0.0118	0.0149	0.0275	64.6
1.5 0.0318	0.0019	0.0080	0.0099	0.0219	68.5
1.3 0.0275	0.0008	0.0041	0.0049	0.0226	81.8
1.0 0.0210	0.0005	0.0034	0.0039	0.0171	82.0

TABLE II

Ammonium persulphate as the source of nitrogen.

Period of incubation : 30-7-47 to 20-9-47.

Original N content Soln. Nitrogen.	Ammon. N left.	Nitric N formed.	Total N left.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
10.0 c.c. 0.3158 g.	0.2428 g.	0.0310 g.	0.2738 g.	0.0420 g.	13.3
7.0 0.2211	0.1472	0.0220	0.1692	0.0519	23.1
5.0 0.1579	0.0888	0.0182	0.1070	0.0590	32.2
3.0 0.0947	0.0272	0.0142	0.0414	0.0533	56.3
1.0 0.0316	0.0000	0.0113	0.0113	0.0203	64.2

TABLE III

Ammonium phosphate as the source of nitrogen. Period of incubation : 20-12-47 to 27-2-48.

Original N content Soln. Nitrogen.	Ammon. N left.	Nitric N formed.	Total N left.	N. lost	% Loss of N.
7.0 c.c. 0.1486 g.	0.0718 g.	0.0180 g.	0.0894 g.	0.0591 g.	39.8
5.0 0.1061	0.0328	0.0072	0.0400	0.0661	62.3
2.0 0.0424	0.0069	0.0055	0.0124	0.0300	70.7

TABLE IV

Gelatine as the source of nitrogen. Period of incubation : 20-12-47 to 27-2-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed	N lost.	% Loss of N.
40.0 c.c. 0.0992 g.	0.0517 g.	0.0072 g.	0.0102 g.	0.0475 g.	47.8
20.0 0.0496	0.0204	0.0017	0.0041	0.0292	58.8
10.0 0.0248	0.0081	0.0008	0.0022	0.0167	67.3

TABLE V

Urea as the source of nitrogen. Period of incubation : 4-8-48 to 23-9-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
0.4286 g. 0.2000 g.	0.1202 g.	0.0101 g.	0.0197 g.	0.0798 g.	39.9
0.2143 0.1000	0.0486	0.0063	0.0122	0.0312	51.2
0.1072 0.0500	0.0198	0.0024	0.0082	0.0302	60.4

TABLE VI

Huppuric acid as the source of nitrogen. Period of incubation: 29-7-48 to 17-9-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
2.5572 g.	0.2000 g.	0.0112 g.	0.0125 g.	0.0798 g.	39.9
1.2786	0.1000	0.0500	0.0087	0.0500	50.0
0.6394	0.0500	0.0210	0.0032	0.0290	58.0

TABLE VII

Oil-cake as the source of nitrogen (Nitrogen content of oil-cake used=5.0%)
Period of incubation : 4-8-48 to 23-9-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
4.0 g.	0.2000 g.	0.1258 g.	0.0064 g.	0.0732 g.	36.6
2.0	0.1000	0.0513	0.0041	0.0487	48.7
1.0	0.0500	0.0213	0.0014	0.0287	57.4

TABLE VIII

Uric acid as the source of nitrogen. Period of incubation : 23-7-48 to 10-9-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
0.80 g.	0.2000 g.	0.1224 g.	0.0062 g.	0.0776 g.	38.8
0.30	0.1000	0.0514	0.0051	0.0486	48.6
0.15	0.0500	0.0218	0.0040	0.0282	56.4

TABLE IX

Fibrin as the source of nitrogen (Nitrogen content of fibrin used=14.7%)
Period of incubation : 29-7-48 to 17-9-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
1.40 g.	0.2058 g.	0.1327 g.	0.0095 g.	0.0731 g.	35.5
0.70	0.1029	0.0601	0.0048	0.0428	41.7
0.35	0.0515	0.0256	0.0019	0.0259	50.3

TABLE X

Creatine as the source of nitrogen. Period of incubation : 23-7-48 to 10-9-48.

Original N content Substance. Nitrogen.	Total N left.	Ammon. N formed.	Nitric N formed.	N lost.	% Loss of N.
0.6238 g.	0.2000 g.	0.1260 g.	0.0081 g.	0.0740 g.	37.0
0.3119	0.1000	0.0538	0.0043	0.0462	46.2
0.1560	0.0500	0.0240	0.0024	0.0260	52.0

DISCUSSION

The foregoing experimental results show that even during the process of nitrification of ammonium salts or other nitrogenous compounds, under conditions quite favourable for the growth of bacteria, there is a considerable loss of nitrogen. The mechanism of reactions involved in liquid cultures appears to be the same as in soil cultures when nitrogenous manures are added to the soil under the field or laboratory conditions.

The loss of nitrogen during the nitrification has been explained by us on the view-point that during nitrification, the ammonium ions and nitrite ions, present simultaneously, combine to give ammonium nitrite, which being an unstable compound decomposes into water and nitrogen. In case of soils having a pH greater than 7, some nitrogen may be lost as ammonia gas; but under ordinary conditions, on adding nitrogenous manures, the pH goes to the acid side and the loss may be partially due to the decomposition of nitrous acid according to the equation:

Our results further show that the loss of nitrogen and the nitrification are much more pronounced with ammonium salts than with other nitrogenous substances. The greater loss in case of ammonium salts is due to the possibility of larger amounts of ammonium nitrite being formed on account of the easy nitrification of the ammonium ions present. In the case of substances like oil-cake, creatine, fibrin and uric acid, the loss is less, as is clear from the following table.

TABLE XI

No.	Substances.	Nitric N. formed.	% Loss of N.	No.	Substances	Nitric N. formed.	% Loss of N.
1.	Ammon. phosphate	7.2mg.	62.3	6.	Oil cake	3.7 mg.	48.7
2.	Ammon. sulphate	15.2	58.4	7.	Uric acid	2.1	48.6
3.	Ammon. persulphate	14.2	56.3	8.	Creatine	2.2	46.2
4.	Urea	12.2	51.2	9.	Fibrin	2.1	41.7
5.	Hippuric acid	7.3	50.0				

In substances other than ammonium salts, the nitrogen is present in a complex condition and hence is slowly nitrified. Moreover, they contain carbon along with nitrogen and the carbonaceous substances present or formed act as negative catalysts and retard the oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds and the consequent loss of nitrogen.